

Post-activity questionnaire

1. How comfortable did you feel wearing the EDA sensor device during Pyramid activity?
1 (*not comfortable*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*Really comfortable*)

2. How comfortable did you feel wearing the temperature sensor device during Pyramid activity, on a scale from 1 to 10?
1 (*not comfortable*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*Really comfortable*)

3. How comfortable did you feel being recorded by a video camera during Pyramid activity, on a scale from 1 to 10?
1 (*not comfortable*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*Really comfortable*)

4. Please evaluate your perceived cognitive load during Pyramid activity on a scale from 1 to 10.
1 (*Low cognitive load*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*High cognitive load*)

5. Evaluate your perception of the stress you experienced throughout the entire class from 1 to 10 (not necessarily related to the cognitive load)
1 (*I didn't feel stressed at all*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*I felt very stressed*)

6. Were there any particularly stressful moments?
Yes - No

If "Yes" in question 6:

About a stressful moment:

7. Could you describe it in detail focusing on the specific emotion (frustration, confusion etc.)? What was the trigger?

8. How stressed did you feel at the moment?
1 (*I didn't feel stressed at all*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*I felt very stressed*)

9. Were there any other particularly stressful moments?
Yes - No

If "Yes" in question 9:

About a stressful moment:

10. Could you describe it in detail focusing on the specific emotion (frustration, confusion etc.)? What was the trigger?

11. How stressed did you feel at the moment?
1 (*I didn't feel stressed at all*) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (*I felt very stressed*)

12. Were there any other particularly stressful moments?

Yes - No

If "Yes" in question 12:

About a stressful moment:

13. Could you describe it in detail focusing on the specific emotion (frustration, confusion etc.)? What was the trigger?

14. How stressed did you feel at the moment?

1 (I didn't feel stressed at all) - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 (I felt very stressed)

If "No" in questions 6, 9 or 12:

Closing remarks

Is there anything else worth mentioning about this session?